

Methodology for: Digitization of Inventories, Wi-Fi Mesh Network Installation in a Forest Environment and Remote Sensing Coverage of Forest Areas Using UAVs:

The Limnia Forest Case Study

DIGIMEDFOR

Digital tools and technology systems for the sustainable management of Mediterranean forest resources

Kavala Municipality Team

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1. Forest Inventory Digitization and Geospatial Data Integration

Methodology

1.1. The task

The primary objective of the proposed digitization methodology framework was the systematic digitization of forest inventory information and associated forestry management datasets for the Limnia Municipal Forest area. The methodology focused on the structured conversion, organization, and standardization of existing analogue and semi-digital forest inventory records into a unified digital geospatial environment suitable for spatial analysis, long-term management, and interoperability with Geographic Information Systems (GIS).

The implemented workflow included the collection, validation, preprocessing, and consolidation of heterogeneous spatial datasets originating from multiple forestry and cartographic sources. These datasets were integrated into a coherent geospatial inventory database designed to support spatial consistency, attribute harmonization, and future analytical processing. Particular emphasis was placed on ensuring compatibility between historical forestry datasets and modern GIS-based spatial management frameworks.

Figure 1, Limnia Forest Map

1.2. Source Spatial Data and Coordinate Reference Systems

The majority of the source spatial layers were originally provided using the Hellenic Geodetic Reference System 1987 (HGRS87 / Greek Grid, commonly referred to as GGRS87 or EPSG:2100), which remains the standard national projected coordinate reference system for most forestry and cadastral datasets in Greece.

However, according to the technical specifications and interoperability requirements of the project, the final geospatial deliverables were required to be distributed in the World Geodetic System 1984 geographic coordinate reference system (WGS84 – EPSG:4326).

For this reason, a dedicated coordinate transformation methodology was implemented in order to convert all required vector datasets from GGRS87 to WGS84 while preserving positional accuracy and spatial consistency. The final outputs, and particularly the Forest Management Spatial Unit (FMSU) polygon boundaries, were therefore exported and delivered as ESRI Shapefiles (.shp) in WGS84 geographic coordinates to ensure compatibility with web mapping platforms, GPS-based field systems, UAV applications, and international geospatial standards.

1.3. Coordinate Transformation and Reprojection Methodology

The reprojection workflow incorporated an explicit and controlled coordinate transformation process between the two coordinate reference systems. Appropriate datum transformation parameters and reprojection settings were applied to minimize spatial distortion and ensure accurate overlay between all spatial layers after transformation.

Additional validation procedures were performed to confirm geometric consistency between the transformed datasets and the original source layers. Projection metadata integrity was also treated as a critical component of the methodology.

Valid and consistent projection definition files (.prj) were preserved and verified throughout the workflow in order to ensure proper interpretation of spatial reference information by third-party GIS software and future users of the dataset.

At the same time, attribute schemas were standardized and normalized across all vector layers to maintain consistency between identifiers, classification fields, management categories, and forestry inventory records during all processing stages.

1.4. Spatial Data Structuring and Attribute Standardization

The methodology included a structured data harmonization process aimed at ensuring consistency between geometry information and associated attribute tables across all forestry datasets.

Figure 2, FMU Map

Attribute schemas were reviewed and standardized in order to maintain compatibility between:

- unique identifiers,
- classification fields,
- management categories,
- forestry inventory attributes, and
- geospatial metadata structures.

This standardization process ensured that all datasets could operate within a common GIS environment without inconsistencies caused by incompatible field structures or naming conventions.

The methodology also ensured that all spatial and attribute information remained interoperable throughout subsequent analytical procedures, reprojection workflows, and spatial overlay operations.

1.5. Spatial Correspondence Analysis of Dominant Species

A central analytical component of the methodology involved the spatial association and transfer of dominant tree-species information derived from the forest management study into the Forest Management Spatial Unit (FMSU) polygons.

Figure 3, FMSU Map

This process was implemented using GIS-based spatial overlay and spatial join methodologies. Forest compartment and stand-level dominant species classifications were spatially intersected with the FMSU polygon boundaries in order to establish topological correspondence between management information and spatial units.

Through this procedure, each FMSU polygon inherited the dominant species characterization associated with the corresponding forest management compartment or stand area.

The methodology therefore enabled the creation of an integrated geospatial forestry inventory in which spatial units were directly linked with forest composition information, improving both analytical usability and operational consistency for future forest management, monitoring, and remote sensing applications.

1.6. Quality Control and Data Validation

In addition to the spatial correspondence procedures, the methodology emphasized the importance of maintaining consistency between geometry and attribute information throughout the entire digitization process.

Quality-control procedures were applied during:

- data conversion,
- reprojection,
- attribute standardization,
- spatial overlay operations, and
- spatial join procedures.

These validation activities aimed to identify and minimize:

- topology inconsistencies,
- duplicate identifiers,
- incomplete attribute transfers,
- geometry mismatches, and
- projection inconsistencies.

The implementation of these quality assurance procedures ensured that the resulting geospatial inventory could support reliable spatial analysis, visualization, and future integration with additional environmental, forestry, and remote sensing datasets.

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2. Wi-Fi Mesh Network Deployment Methodology in Forest Environments

2.1. System Design Methodology and Deployment Scope

The Wi-Fi mesh network methodology was developed to support reliable wireless connectivity within a forest environment characterized by vegetation density, irregular terrain morphology, and the absence of permanent telecommunications infrastructure. The methodology was applied in the context of the Limnia Forest case study and focused on the deployment of a field-operational wireless mesh architecture capable of supporting localized communication, remote sensing operations, UAV activities, field administration, and intermittent data synchronization.

The proposed methodology includes the engineering design, selection, and dimensioning of all major network components, including:

- Wi-Fi mesh access points (APs),
- L2/L3 switching infrastructure,
- routing and gateway systems,
- distributed power stations,
- solar photovoltaic (PV) charging systems, and
- environmental protection infrastructure for outdoor installation.

Special emphasis was placed on modular deployment, maintainability, incremental scalability, and operational resilience under forest conditions. Unlike conventional urban deployments, the installation methodology specifically addressed the challenges associated with dense vegetation attenuation, limited line-of-sight conditions, and off-grid energy requirements.

2.2. Forest Site Survey and Geospatial Planning Methodology

A dedicated forest field survey methodology was implemented prior to installation activities. The survey process included the identification of operational routes, accessibility conditions, terrain obstacles, vegetation density, and potential mounting locations for networking infrastructure. Particular attention was given to the fact that the Wi-Fi mesh infrastructure would be physically installed inside the forest environment, requiring careful adaptation to natural obstacles and environmental constraints.

The identified routes and installation corridors were transferred into a geospatial reference framework in order to support engineering-level planning and infrastructure positioning. The methodology incorporated:

- line-of-sight estimation,
- obstruction mapping,

- vegetation attenuation assessment,
- accessibility evaluation for maintenance operations,
- mounting feasibility analysis, and
- RF propagation approximation.

Figure 4, Main stations sites

Based on these analyses, an initial node placement plan was developed defining the proposed locations for:

- Wi-Fi mesh relay nodes,
- aggregation and distribution switches,
- the central router/gateway,
- battery stations, and
- solar charging units.

The methodology also acknowledged that the initially proposed AP positions represented a baseline deployment configuration that could later be refined during the implementation phase through real RF measurements such as RSSI, SNR, channel occupancy, and obstruction validation tests.

2.3. RF Coverage Modeling Methodology

The wireless coverage methodology was based on categorized RF service zones to facilitate deployment evaluation and post-installation optimization. Coverage estimation was initially derived from RF planning assumptions and environmental propagation characteristics specific to forest environments.

Figure 5, Wi-Fi Mesh Access Points

The methodology classified network service areas into:

- core coverage zones,
- usable coverage zones, and
- fringe or marginal connectivity zones.

This categorization enabled:

- acceptance testing,
- commissioning verification,
- targeted optimization procedures,
- channel reuse planning,
- transmit power adjustment,
- antenna orientation refinement, and
- backhaul quality validation.

The implementation methodology estimated an effective operational coverage area of approximately 45,000 m², with an additional surrounding fringe coverage area of approximately 50,000 m² suitable only for intermittent connectivity under favorable propagation conditions.

2.4. Off-Grid Power Infrastructure Methodology

Since the Wi-Fi mesh system was installed directly within the forest and outside conventional electrical infrastructure, the deployment methodology incorporated a fully off-grid distributed energy architecture.

The network was designed to operate through multiple autonomous battery stations recharged using solar photovoltaic panels.

The proposed methodology treated the energy subsystem as an integral component of the network architecture rather than an auxiliary system. The methodology included:

- node-level energy budgeting,
- seasonal PV variability estimation,
- battery autonomy calculations,
- DC power conversion efficiency assessment,
- cable loss estimation,
- charging cycle planning, and
- operational energy optimization policies.

The distributed power topology was selected in order to:

- minimize single points of failure,
- simplify incremental expansion,
- localize maintenance operations,
- improve resilience under forest conditions, and
- reduce dependency on centralized infrastructure.

Figure 6, Wi-Fi Mesh Coverage

2.5. Operational Performance Assessment Methodology

Field evaluation activities demonstrated that the Wi-Fi mesh deployment methodology was capable of supporting the operational requirements of the project under the environmental conditions of the Limnia Forest area. The deployed infrastructure adequately supported localized communication, commissioning activities, field administration tasks, and intermittent data synchronization inside the forest operational zones.

However, the methodology also documented significant limitations associated with dense forest environments. The results indicated that conventional Wi-Fi mesh architectures become progressively less effective under heavy vegetation and non-line-of-sight (NLoS) conditions due to:

- increased attenuation,
- signal scattering,
- reduced effective range,
- unstable backhaul links, and
- degraded coverage continuity.

The methodology therefore concluded that denser forest environments would require substantially higher infrastructure density, including additional relay nodes, mounting locations, and distributed power stations, resulting in increased deployment complexity and maintenance requirements.

2.6. Recommended Future Methodological Improvements

Based on the findings of the Limnia Forest implementation, the methodology recommends the adoption of hybrid communication architectures for future deployments in heavily vegetated environments.

The proposed evolution strategy suggests maintaining Wi-Fi mesh networking for localized high-throughput requirements while integrating complementary long-range and low-power communication technologies for telemetry and distributed sensing applications. Recommended candidate technologies include:

- LoRaWAN,
- NB-IoT/LTE-M, and
- Wi-Fi HaLow (IEEE 802.11ah).

2.7. Pre-Operational Testing and Validation Methodology

The deployment methodology incorporated a structured pre-operational testing framework prior to network commissioning. The testing procedures included:

Configuration Validation

- Verification of hardware conformity,
- firmware synchronization,

- IP/VLAN planning validation,
- security configuration checks, and
- management access verification.

Power System Validation

- Voltage/current/power measurements,
- battery autonomy validation,
- PV charging verification,
- DC conversion efficiency checks, and
- protection mechanism testing.

RF Validation

- Noise floor measurements,
- channel occupancy analysis,
- interference detection,
- propagation verification, and
- vegetation attenuation assessment.

Backhaul Acceptance Testing

- RSSI and SNR measurements,
- packet loss and latency analysis,
- throughput validation, and
- hop-depth performance assessment.

Coverage Verification

- Structured walk-testing,
- service zone validation,
- shadow area identification, and
- corrective optimization procedures.

Resilience and Failover Testing

- Mesh self-healing validation,
- rerouting verification,
- reboot recovery testing, and
- configuration persistence evaluation.

Security and Management Verification

- Encryption validation,
- firewall policy checks,
- management isolation verification, and
- logging/NTP synchronization validation.

The final go/no-go commissioning decision was based on the successful satisfaction of predefined RF, coverage, resilience, autonomy, and security acceptance thresholds.

2.8. Sources

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3. Remote Sensing Coverage of Forest Areas Using UAVs

3.1. Introduction and Operational Objectives

The primary objective of the HD drone methodology developed for the Limnia Forest case study was the acquisition of high-detail canopy-level imagery suitable for advanced photogrammetric processing, forest monitoring applications, environmental assessment, and geospatial analysis workflows. The methodology was specifically designed for forest environments characterized by dense vegetation, rapidly changing terrain elevation, irregular canopy morphology, and operational visibility constraints.

The implemented workflow focused on the development of a repeatable operational methodology capable of ensuring:

- stable image acquisition,
- repeatable overlap geometry,
- controlled flight clearance above canopy surfaces,
- reliable downstream photogrammetric processing,
- operational safety under forest conditions, and
- consistent georeferenced outputs.

Particular emphasis was placed on achieving canopy-level coverage while maintaining safe operational margins and minimizing the effects of vegetation movement, terrain irregularities, localized turbulence, and flight instability. Unlike conventional photogrammetric operations over open terrain, forest environments introduce dynamic environmental variables that significantly affect both flight execution and data quality. These include rapidly changing illumination conditions, partial GNSS obstruction, canopy-induced turbulence, limited emergency landing opportunities, and highly variable canopy elevation profiles.

The methodology therefore incorporated conservative operational assumptions and multiple validation stages in order to improve mission repeatability and reduce operational uncertainty. The project further demonstrated that successful canopy-level acquisition within forest environments cannot rely exclusively on standard automated grid workflows. Instead, such operations require a combination of:

- field-validated operational geometry,
- locally accurate elevation references,
- carefully selected UAV platforms,
- conservative safety margins,

- controlled photographic parameterization,
- segmented multi-sortie mission planning,
- continuous field verification procedures, and
- detailed regulatory and operational compliance frameworks.

The resulting framework therefore represents not only a UAV image acquisition workflow, but also an integrated operational methodology for conducting low-altitude drone missions in complex forest environments where canopy structure, terrain variability, and operational accessibility substantially affect flight safety and photogrammetric consistency.

3.2. Regulatory and Standards Framework for UAS Flight Operations

The operational methodology was developed within the broader European and national regulatory framework governing Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS). At European level, there is no single standalone standard governing all drone operations. Instead, the applicable framework consists of a layered combination of:

- binding European regulations,
- acceptable means of compliance and guidance material,
- operational risk-assessment methodologies, and
- complementary international standards.

The primary legal framework governing UAS operations within the European Union is Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947, which establishes the operational rules and procedures applicable to unmanned aircraft systems and defines the three operational categories:

- Open,
- Specific, and
- Certified.

This regulation defines:

- operator obligations,
- remote pilot competency requirements,
- operational limitations,
- authorization procedures,

- operational categorization methodologies, and
- flight execution requirements.

In parallel, UAS platform classification and technical conformity requirements are governed under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 and its amendment Regulation (EU) 2020/1058, which introduced the C5 and C6 UAS classes intended for operations under the Specific category. These regulations establish the technical conformity framework for UAS platforms placed on the European market and define the complete class structure (C0–C6).

The methodology additionally incorporated the principles of EASA AMC/GM (Acceptable Means of Compliance / Guidance Material), which provide practical interpretation and operational compliance pathways for operators and national aviation authorities. These documents address:

- operational categorization,
- organizational procedures,
- pilot competency,
- technical requirements,
- operational limitations, and
- operational safety procedures applicable to UAS deployments.

For operations potentially extending beyond the Open category, the methodology acknowledged the relevance of the Specific Operations Risk Assessment (SORA) framework, originally developed by JARUS and subsequently adopted by EASA. SORA provides a structured methodology for evaluating:

- Ground Risk Class (GRC),
- Air Risk Class (ARC),
- Specific Assurance and Integrity Level (SAIL), and
- Operational Safety Objectives (OSOs).

The methodology recognized that forest operations, especially in mountainous or remote terrain, may present operational conditions requiring enhanced operational assessment even when missions are conducted under Visual Line of Sight (VLOS). Particular operational considerations include:

- terrain-related containment limitations,
- rapidly changing canopy elevation,

- forestry roads and trails,
- seasonal visitors,
- machinery activity,
- limited accessibility,
- partial GNSS obstruction, and
- complex airspace interactions.

Where applicable, predefined compliance pathways such as PDRA and Standard Scenarios (STS) may provide simplified operational routes under predefined conditions. In particular, STS-02 may be relevant for certain BVLOS scenarios conducted over sparsely populated areas with controlled ground zones, although its applicability within mountainous forest terrain may be operationally constrained due to the difficulty of maintaining effective containment areas.

The methodology additionally recognized the supporting role of international standards including:

- ISO 21384-3:2023,
- ASTM F3196,
- ASTM F3269, and
- ASTM F3322.

These standards contribute supporting guidance regarding:

- BVLOS approval methodologies,
- operational best practices,
- flight behavior limitation procedures,
- parachute recovery systems, and
- broader operational safety documentation.

At national level, all operations were considered within the jurisdiction of the Hellenic Civil Aviation Authority (HCAA), which implements and supervises the European regulatory framework within Greece. The methodology also incorporated mandatory geo-zone verification using Drone Aware GR (DAGR) prior to all mission activities in order to identify:

- prohibited airspace,

- temporary restrictions,
- controlled airspace interactions,
- military areas, and
- operational authorization requirements.

The integration of regulatory procedures directly into the operational methodology significantly improved operational consistency, strengthened safety assurance, and reduced legal and operational uncertainty throughout the project lifecycle.

3.3. Operational Considerations for Forested Environments

Operations over forested environments introduce substantial operational, technical, and regulatory complexities compared to conventional UAV deployments over open terrain or urban environments. Forest environments are characterized by:

- dense canopy structures,
- reduced visibility,
- rapidly changing terrain elevation,
- partial GNSS obstruction,
- non-line-of-sight propagation conditions,
- unstable illumination conditions,
- limited emergency landing areas, and
- difficult accessibility.

These environmental conditions directly influence:

- flight stability,
- communication reliability,
- UAV positioning consistency,
- image overlap geometry,
- emergency response procedures,
- operational predictability, and

- photogrammetric reconstruction quality.

The methodology therefore adopted conservative operational assumptions even for VLOS operations.

Particular emphasis was placed on:

- segmented mission execution,
- continuous field validation,
- conservative containment assumptions,
- operational redundancy,
- continuous situational awareness, and
- strict pre-operational validation procedures.

Special consideration was also given to the interaction between canopy geometry and low-altitude flight stability. Dense canopy structures create localized turbulence and unpredictable aerodynamic effects, particularly when UAVs operate close to vegetation surfaces. Additionally, shadows, high-frequency canopy textures, and rapidly changing illumination conditions significantly affect image quality and photogrammetric consistency.

The methodology therefore recognized that safe canopy-level acquisition requires:

- carefully controlled operating heights,
- conservative speed selection,
- stable image exposure settings,
- locally accurate elevation models, and
- continuous monitoring of environmental conditions throughout flight execution.

3.4. Area of Interest (AOI) Definition and Field Reconnaissance

The first stage of the methodology involved the detailed delineation of the Area of Interest (AOI) and the definition of operational acquisition objectives. The AOI was evaluated according to:

- canopy density,
- elevation variability,

- terrain accessibility,
- forest structure,
- vegetation continuity, and
- photogrammetric acquisition requirements.

A systematic field reconnaissance methodology was subsequently implemented throughout the operational area. The reconnaissance procedures included:

- on-foot inspection of operational corridors,
- hazard identification,
- slope assessment,
- obstacle mapping,
- dense understory evaluation,
- identification of emergency access routes, and
- selection of suitable take-off and landing locations.

The selected TOL points were specifically positioned to preserve continuous Visual Line of Sight (VLOS) during all flight operations, since vegetation density and terrain relief were found to rapidly obstruct UAV visibility during low-altitude canopy missions.

Mission planning activities further demonstrated that the AOI could not be safely covered within a single sortie using the available UAV platforms. Consequently, the operational methodology decomposed the survey into multiple segmented sub-blocks, each associated with:

- a dedicated TOL point,
- predefined flight boundaries,
- predictable endurance limits,
- conservative battery reserve margins, and
- controlled overlap objectives.

The reconnaissance phase additionally enabled the identification of:

- potential emergency landing areas,

- localized RF disturbances,
- terrain accessibility limitations,
- canopy sections presenting elevated operational risk, and
- environmental conditions capable of affecting flight stability.

This preliminary terrain understanding significantly improved operational predictability and reduced uncertainty during subsequent acquisition stages.

3.5. UAV Platforms and Operational Role Allocation

The methodology incorporated the use of two distinct UAV platforms, each assigned a specific operational role within the workflow.

The DJI Phantom 4 Pro was selected as the primary photogrammetric acquisition platform due to its superior imaging characteristics and operational suitability for high-detail mapping missions. Operationally significant features included:

- a 20 MP one-inch class sensor,
- adjustable aperture,
- mechanical shutter operation, and
- reduced rolling-shutter distortion during movement.

Figure 7, DJI Phantom 4 Pro

This platform was therefore prioritized for final mapping missions intended to generate the principal project deliverables, including:

- orthomosaics,
- DSM products,
- canopy-level imagery, and
- photogrammetric reconstruction datasets.

The DJI Mini 2 SE was used primarily as a reconnaissance and auxiliary operational platform. Its deployment focused on:

- rapid field deployment,
- visual inspection of canopy conditions,
- validation of operational corridors,
- relocation or confirmation of TOL points, and
- preservation of VLOS conditions without utilizing primary mapping resources.

Figure 8, DJI Mini 2 SE

The separation of operational roles between the two UAV platforms improved operational flexibility, reduced unnecessary utilization of the primary mapping platform, and increased overall mission efficiency during field deployment activities.

3.6. Manual Flight Validation and Feasibility Testing

Prior to automated mission execution, the methodology incorporated a dedicated manual flight validation phase intended to evaluate operational conditions that could not be fully predicted during desktop planning procedures.

Manual test flights were performed at progressively lower operating heights in order to assess:

- canopy-level wind behavior,
- localized turbulence effects,
- GNSS stability under partial sky obstruction,
- pilot workload under VLOS constraints,
- obstacle-clearance margins, and
- image sharpness under variable forest illumination conditions.

The methodology also evaluated the interaction between canopy proximity and photogrammetric consistency. Early low-altitude trials demonstrated that operating excessively close to the canopy surface reduced image repeatability due to:

- foliage movement,
- localized aerodynamic instability,
- rotor-induced turbulence,
- rapid illumination changes, and
- unstable overlap geometry.

Consequently, the final operational methodology adopted a conservative minimum acquisition clearance of approximately 10 meters above the canopy surface in order to improve:

- image stability,
- radiometric consistency,
- motion sharpness,
- overlap reliability, and
- downstream photogrammetric robustness.

3.7. Evaluation of DEM-Based Automated Flight Planning

The methodology initially explored the feasibility of automated terrain-following missions using publicly available Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and cadastre-related elevation products.

Automated grid flight trials were conducted using elevation layers obtained from common web-based sources and alternative elevation datasets in order to evaluate whether these surfaces could reliably support low-altitude canopy-following operations.

However, the methodology documented several critical limitations associated with these elevation sources, including:

- insufficient spatial resolution,
- smoothing of local canopy variability,
- inconsistent elevation definitions,
- orthometric versus ellipsoidal height discrepancies,
- CRS transformation inconsistencies, and
- horizontal or vertical misalignment during reprojection.

These limitations produced unacceptable fluctuations in canopy clearance and inconsistent flight geometry, particularly in areas characterized by dense vegetation and rapidly changing terrain elevation. Additionally, inconsistencies between different DEM sources created operational uncertainty regarding true canopy clearance, reducing the reliability of automated low-altitude missions.

The methodology therefore concluded that publicly available DEM products alone could not reliably support safe and repeatable canopy-level operations within the Limnia Forest environment. This conclusion motivated the development of a locally generated DSM-based workflow specifically optimized for forest applications.

3.8. Local DSM Production Methodology

To address the limitations identified during DEM evaluation, the methodology was redesigned into a two-stage acquisition workflow.

The first stage involved the execution of higher-altitude survey flights specifically intended for the generation of a local Digital Surface Model (DSM). The purpose of the DSM was to provide a high-resolution operational surface capable of accurately representing:

- canopy elevation,

- local topographic variability,
- vegetation structure, and
- micro-relief conditions.

Particular emphasis was placed on maintaining geometric integrity and georeferencing consistency because the DSM would subsequently be used as an operational flight-planning surface rather than solely as a visualization product.

Figure 9, DSM

The resulting DSM was exported with a raster cell size significantly finer than 0.25 meters, enabling substantially improved representation of canopy geometry compared to generic public DEM datasets.

The methodology also recognized that spatial resolution alone does not guarantee vertical accuracy. Consequently, additional validation procedures were incorporated in order to confirm:

- DSM consistency,
- georeferencing integrity,
- surface continuity,
- absence of severe artifacts, and
- compatibility with downstream mission-planning software.

This DSM-based approach significantly reduced uncertainty associated with canopy clearance estimation and

improved operational safety during subsequent low-altitude acquisition missions.

3.9. DSM-Based Mission Planning with UGCS

Following DSM production, the methodology incorporated DSM-driven mission planning using UGCS software.

The workflow included:

- DSM import validation,
- CRS alignment verification,
- georeferencing consistency checks, and
- operational surface positioning confirmation.

Final mapping missions were then designed to maintain approximately 10 meters above the DSM surface, enabling true canopy-surface following rather than conventional terrain-only following.

This DSM-referenced methodology significantly improved:

- altitude stability,
- overlap uniformity,
- footprint consistency,
- operational predictability, and
- low-altitude safety margins.

The segmented multi-sortie structure remained an integral part of the methodology in order to preserve VLOS conditions and accommodate UAV endurance limitations.

The methodology additionally demonstrated that DSM-based planning substantially reduced abrupt altitude corrections commonly observed when using generic DEM products. This resulted in:

- smoother flight behavior,
- improved image overlap consistency,
- reduced canopy-collision risk,
- improved flight-path predictability, and
- more stable downstream photogrammetric reconstruction.

The integration of locally generated surface models into mission planning therefore constituted one of the most critical operational improvements achieved during the project.

3.10. Photographic Parameterization and Motion Optimization

The methodology treated image quality as a combined function of camera parameterization and UAV motion dynamics. Particular attention was given to the relationship between flight speed and motion blur, especially over fine canopy textures characterized by high-frequency spatial detail.

Figure 10, Blurred and overexposed image (ISO 100, f/4.5, 1/125, Auto)

Iterative testing procedures resulted in the selection of the following operational acquisition parameters:

- Aperture: f/4 to f/8,
- Flight speed: 1–2 m/s,
- Shutter speed: 1/400 to 1/1000 s,
- Maximum ISO: 400.

These settings were selected in order to:

- minimize motion blur,
- reduce image noise,
- preserve overlap consistency,

- improve tie-point extraction reliability, and
- support stable photogrammetric reconstruction workflows.

Figure 11. Correct Sharp Image (ISO 400,f/8,1/800)

The methodology additionally recognized that excessive UAV speed significantly increases the probability of motion-induced blur, particularly over highly detailed canopy textures. For this reason, conservative flight speeds were adopted despite the resulting increase in acquisition duration.

Special attention was also given to illumination variability caused by forest shadows and canopy openings. Exposure parameters were therefore optimized in order to maintain:

- radiometric consistency,
- sufficient shadow detail,
- reduced highlight clipping, and
- stable image sharpness across varying environmental conditions.

These parameterization procedures significantly improved the quality and usability of the acquired imagery for downstream DSM and orthomosaic generation workflows.

3.11. Finalized Operational Methodology

The principal outcome of the project was the development of a repeatable and operationally validated methodology for UAV-based forest coverage in environments characterized by rapid elevation variation and

complex canopy structures.

Figure 12, Project planning in UGCS

The finalized workflow was defined as:

1. AOI definition and ground reconnaissance,
2. manual feasibility flights,
3. DEM and elevation-source evaluation,
4. identification of CRS and datum inconsistencies,
5. higher-altitude survey acquisition,
6. local sub-25 cm DSM generation,
7. DSM import into UGCS,
8. DSM-referenced low-altitude planning,
9. final camera and motion optimization,
10. segmented canopy-level acquisition missions.

The methodology demonstrated that successful low-altitude canopy mapping requires both:

- field-validated operational geometry, and
- a locally accurate and vertically consistent surface reference.

Figure 13, Mission acquired images centroids

Using this methodology, the final missions successfully produced imagery and derived datasets sufficient for the objectives of the project despite the challenging forest environment and complex canopy dynamics.

The project also demonstrated that successful UAV deployment in forest environments depends not only on photogrammetric quality, but equally on:

- operational adaptability,
- conservative flight planning,
- continuous environmental validation,
- detailed pre-operational assessment,
- robust regulatory compliance, and
- integration between operational and geospatial workflows.

The finalized methodology therefore provides a transferable operational framework suitable for future forest-monitoring, environmental-mapping, and canopy-analysis applications under similarly demanding environmental conditions.

3.12. Pre-Operational Testing and Validation Procedures

The methodology incorporated a structured pre-operational validation framework prior to final mission execution. The testing procedures included:

Regulatory and Airspace Compliance

- Geo-zone verification using Drone Aware GR (DAGR),
- HCAA authorization validation,
- operational category confirmation,
- restriction analysis, and
- day-of-operation compliance checks.

These procedures ensured that all missions remained compliant with both national and European aviation requirements prior to deployment.

Desktop Validation

- CRS and vertical reference auditing,
- DSM quality inspection,
- hillshade and contour review,
- UGCS mission verification, and
- climb/descent rate validation.

These validation procedures significantly reduced the probability of mission-planning inconsistencies and operational anomalies during canopy-following operations.

UAS Readiness Checks

- Firmware verification,
- battery health inspection,
- storage capacity validation,
- IMU and compass status checks,
- gimbal stabilization verification, and
- lens cleanliness inspection.

RF and GNSS Validation

- Satellite stability checks,

- HDOP/VDOP monitoring,
- control link verification, and
- interference assessment.

Safety Functional Flights

- Hover stability testing,
- RTH validation,
- braking behavior assessment, and
- low-speed operational verification.

Image Quality Validation

- On-site sharpness inspection,
- motion blur assessment,
- exposure validation,
- shadow-noise evaluation, and
- overlap consistency testing.

DSM Clearance Verification

- DSM-following validation,
- abrupt altitude correction monitoring,
- canopy-clearance confirmation, and
- climb/descent safety verification.

Endurance and Go/No-Go Validation

- Battery endurance assessment,
- reserve margin confirmation,
- operational threshold verification, and
- final go/no-go authorization procedures.

The final operational approval process required successful validation of:

- regulatory compliance,
- UAV readiness,
- RF and GNSS stability,
- image quality consistency,
- canopy-clearance integrity,
- endurance margins, and
- operational safety thresholds.

Only after successful completion of all validation stages was the mission considered operationally ready for final canopy-level data acquisition.

3.13. Sources

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